

ISic4394

Sikel inscription

Language

Sikel

Type

unknown

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

none

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Palike

Place of origin (modern)

Area archeologica di Palikè

Provenance

Orsi 1900 reports that it was found c.1878 on the rock outcrop of ancient Palike, but subsequently sent to Rome (Ecole Francaise?) and lost; Orsi only saw a drawing

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not recorded mm

Text

1. ΟΣΤΙΥΗΑΥΕΚ

2. ΕΙΔ

Apparatus

Text after Orsi and Agostiniani

Translation

Commentary

the sole record of this text is the report in Orsi 1900, reporting the discovery, his inability to locate it, and reproducing the drawing provided by the unnamed discoverer

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 59 no.37

Agostiniani, L. 1992. Les parlers indigenes de la Sicile pregreceque. *Lalies*. 11: 126-157. At 149 no.10

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Γ Δ ∟ Ι Γ √
Ε

Drawing of P.Orsi